

THE EDUCATIONAL DIMENSION OF SUSTAINABILITY

Emil LAZĂR¹

¹University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract

Education for Sustainable Development represents one of the essential directions of the postmodern educational paradigm, being oriented toward the formation of a culture of individual and collective responsibility in relation to the environment, society, and the economy. This article explores the educational dimension of sustainability by analyzing its implications for educational policies, curriculum design, and the development of competences for global citizenship. The principles promoted by UNESCO and the European sustainability competence framework (GreenComp, 2022) are highlighted, emphasizing the role of the teacher as a facilitator of change and a promoter of transformative learning.

Keywords: sustainability; education for sustainable development; green competences; curriculum; teacher education.

Theoretical Foundations of Sustainability in Education

The concept of sustainability, understood as an integrative paradigm connecting the ecological, economic, and social dimensions, has its theoretical origins in the report *Our Common Future* issued by the World Commission on Environment and Development (1987). The Brundtland Report defined sustainable development as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (WCED, 1987, p. 43). This formulation introduced, for the first time in political and educational discourse, an ethical perspective on the interdependence between people, resources, and ecosystems, emphasizing equity, intergenerational solidarity, and collective responsibility.

From an educational perspective, sustainability subsequently became a framework concept for reforming education systems, associated with the need for transformative learning capable of generating changes in values, behaviors, and social structures. Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), promoted by UNESCO, derives directly from the principles of the Brundtland Report, proposing an educational model that goes beyond knowledge transmission and aims at developing systemic and reflective thinking. According to UNESCO (2020), education represents the key to the transition toward a sustainable society, as “for our own survival, we must learn to live sustainably on this planet” (p. 5). This perspective implies not only a change in curricular content, but also a reconfiguration of the entire institutional culture through an integrated, participatory, and interdisciplinary approach.

The theoretical framework of educational sustainability, consolidated through the document *Education for Sustainable Development: A Roadmap* (UNESCO, 2020), highlights the need to reorient education toward the development of competences for action and critical reflection. *ESD for 2030* defines five priority areas of intervention: integrating sustainability into

educational policies, transforming learning environments, strengthening teachers' capacities, empowering youth, and accelerating sustainable actions at the local level. In this sense, education becomes an instrument of empowerment, a process of awareness-raising and civic mobilization through which individuals are prepared to actively participate in building a fair and ecologically balanced common future. This direction aligns with the paradigm of transformative learning (Mezirow, 1997), which argues that authentic education involves a critical revision of personal and social frames of reference, leading to informed and responsible action.

At the European level, the theoretical foundations of educational sustainability are reinforced through **GreenComp – The European Sustainability Competence Framework** (European Commission, 2022). GreenComp defines sustainability as a set of cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioral competences designed to develop “ways of thinking, planning, and acting with empathy, responsibility, and care for the planet and for public health” (Bianchi, Pisiotis, & Cabrera, 2022, p. 2). The proposed model includes four interdependent theoretical domains: embracing sustainability values (with an emphasis on equity and respect for nature), embracing complexity (through systemic and critical thinking), envisioning sustainable futures (through anticipatory literacy and adaptability), and acting for sustainability (through individual initiative and collective action).

This conceptual framework reflects a systemic approach to learning, inspired by theories of complexity (Morin, 2005) and the paradigm of ecopedagogy (Gadotti, 2008), according to which education must reorient the human–nature relationship from exploitation to coexistence. In this sense, sustainability becomes not merely a transversal curriculum theme, but an educational philosophy integrating the ethical, ecological, and economic

dimensions of human development. Barth et al. (2007) emphasize that sustainable education should promote “systemic thinking, future orientation, collaboration capacity, and responsible decision-making” (p. 418), competences fully embedded in the GreenComp structure.

From an epistemological perspective, the theoretical foundations of sustainability in education rely on the idea of interdependence between knowledge and action. Wiek, Withycombe, and Redman (2011) formulated the sustainability competence model - systemic, anticipatory, normative, strategic, and interpersonal - highlighting that education cannot contribute to social transformation without a coherent integration of these dimensions. This vision is reiterated by UNESCO (2020), which stresses that Education for Sustainable Development should not be reduced to a separate discipline, but infused into all curricular areas as a transversal axiological and methodological matrix.

Another major theoretical foundation of educational sustainability is the holistic and transdisciplinary approach. Sterling (2001) described education for sustainability as a process of “systemic learning” that requires shifting the educational paradigm from a transmissive model to a reflective–participatory one. In a world marked by multiple crises - ecological, economic, social, and cultural - sustainability presupposes understanding global complexity and cultivating planetary consciousness (UNESCO, 2019; Morin, 2005).

Therefore, the theoretical foundations of sustainability in education can be synthesized into four major conceptual directions: (1) the intergenerational and ethical character of development derived from the Brundtland Report (WCED, 1987); (2) the role of education as a driver of social and ecological transformation promoted by UNESCO through ESD for 2030; (3) the competence-based and systemic perspective on learning embodied in GreenComp (European Commission, 2022); and (4) the orientation toward transformative and reflective

learning in line with Mezirow (1997) and Sterling (2001). Together, these dimensions define a pedagogy of planetary responsibility based on critical thinking, empathy, and cooperation, transforming education into a process of constructing a sustainable common future.

International Policies and Frameworks on Educational Sustainability

Educational sustainability has become, in recent decades, a central pillar of the global development agenda, recognized as an essential condition for achieving balance between social progress, environmental protection, and economic growth. Beginning with the Brundtland Report (WCED, 1987), the idea that education must ensure not only knowledge transmission but also the formation of ethical and ecological awareness has become a guiding principle of international policies. Since then, major global actors - UNESCO, the United Nations, OECD, and the European Union—have shaped a complex architecture of normative frameworks and strategies aimed at integrating sustainability into educational policies and lifelong learning processes.

The first major moment of global convergence in this respect was the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (Rio de Janeiro, 1992), which launched **Agenda 21**, a reference document that established education as “the primary instrument for promoting sustainable development and changing individual and collective behavior” (United Nations, 1992, Chapter 36). This was followed by the **Johannesburg Declaration** (2002), which reaffirmed the role of education as a vector of sustainability and recommended integrating ecological and ethical principles at all levels of education.

In 2005, the United Nations, through UNESCO, launched the **Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (2005-2014)**, aiming to reorient education systems toward competence and value formation for a sustainable society. The Decade’s framework document emphasized that education must

“teach people to think critically, take responsibility for the present and the future, and act in the spirit of global solidarity” (UNESCO, 2005, p. 8). This vision marked a paradigmatic shift in international educational policies - from information transmission to value, attitude, and behavior transformation.

The natural successor of the Decade was the **Global Action Programme on Education for Sustainable Development (GAP, 2015-2019)**, which provided an operational framework for implementing ESD principles at national and local levels. GAP promoted a multi-level, multi-actor governance model, encouraging partnerships between educational institutions, local authorities, the private sector, and civil society. This model directly influenced the adoption, in 2015, of the **2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development**, which includes the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Within the 2030 Agenda, **Goal 4 – Quality Education** includes Target 4.7, which stipulates that “by 2030, all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity” (United Nations, 2015, p. 21). This target represents the normative foundation of educational sustainability worldwide.

To support the implementation of the 2030 Agenda, UNESCO published in 2020 the strategic document *Education for Sustainable Development: A Roadmap*, which defines the conceptual framework of ESD for the next decade. UNESCO (2020) reinterprets education as a transformative process capable of shaping individual and collective consciousness in relation to global challenges, stating that “every education system has the responsibility to lead the transformation toward a more just and sustainable future”.

At the European level, educational policy on sustainability is guided by the **European Green Deal** (2019) and by European Commission initiatives on competences for a green and digital economy. In 2022, the Commission launched **GreenComp**, developed by the Joint Research Centre, offering a unified model for integrating sustainability competences into formal and non-formal education. GreenComp promotes a systemic vision of sustainability education based on embracing values, complexity, future thinking, and collective action (Bianchi et al., 2022).

All these international frameworks converge toward a new educational paradigm in which sustainability becomes a universal value and a criterion of public policy quality. Education is no longer viewed solely as knowledge transmission, but as a mechanism of social and ecological governance.

Sustainability Competences in the University Curriculum: Theoretical Perspectives and Integration Directions

In contemporary higher education, sustainability education is no longer a marginal option but a transversal curriculum dimension and a criterion of institutional quality. Universities are called upon to educate graduates capable of systemic thinking, ethical action, and responsible social engagement. According to UNESCO (2020), integrating sustainability into university curricula requires a paradigmatic shift - from discipline-centered education to transdisciplinary, reflective, and transformative learning.

Wiek et al. (2011) propose a solid competence model for sustainability education, defining five essential competences: systems thinking, anticipatory competence, normative competence, strategic competence, and interpersonal competence. These competences align with GreenComp (European Commission, 2022) and can be operationalized in university curricula through learning objectives, active pedagogies, and authentic assessment.

Curricula for sustainability must be transformative and integrative, emphasizing project-based learning, real-world problem solving, community engagement, and applied research. Sterling (2001) argues that sustainability education cannot be achieved through add-on courses, but through a paradigmatic restructuring of the university itself.

The Managerial Dimension of Educational Sustainability

Educational sustainability also involves transforming how institutions are led, organized, and evaluated. UNESCO (2020) promotes a **whole-institution approach**, requiring sustainability integration in governance, planning, curriculum, learning environments, and community relations.

Sustainable educational leadership is defined by Hargreaves and Fink (2006) as leadership that builds deep learning, supports all learners, and conserves human and material resources for future generations. From this perspective, sustainable management integrates ethical values, participatory governance, and long-term vision.

Universities and schools become **learning organizations** (Senge, 1990), capable of systemic reflection, collaboration, and continuous adaptation. Sustainable management thus becomes a catalyst for cultural transformation.

Educational Implications and Strategies for Implementing Sustainability in the University

Universities play a crucial role as catalysts of sustainability, acting as civic hubs that integrate education, research, and social responsibility. Sustainable universities “live sustainability,” embedding ecological and ethical principles into curricula, governance, and community engagement (Sterling, 2001).

Implementing sustainability requires integrated institutional strategies, including sustainability offices, green campus plans, interdisciplinary research, and teacher professional development. Students are engaged through project-

based learning, service learning, and applied research addressing real societal challenges.

General Conclusions on Educational Sustainability

Educational sustainability represents a profound paradigm shift - from fragmented knowledge to integrated thinking, from individual performance to collective responsibility, from short-term efficiency to long-term relevance. It positions education as the primary driver of social and ecological transformation.

As UNESCO (2020) emphasizes, “we cannot build a sustainable future without education that teaches people how to think, not what to think.” Educational sustainability thus becomes both the goal and the method of twenty-first-century education.

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